

HYSTEPS – HYBRID STORAGE FOR EFFICIENT PROCESSES

“The increase of renewable energy sources and the progressing decarbonization require a drastic capacity increase of the thermal energy storage in existing industrial plants.”

GERWIN DREXLER-SCHMID,
Project Manager HyStEPs, Austrian Institute of Technology

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KEY FACTS

Application in energy-intensive industries: paper, chemicals, food, iron & steel

CO₂ savings potential of 11 million tonnes per year in the EU

Market potential of €550 millions in the EU

Duration: 09/18 - 09/21

Project volume: €800,000

An innovative hybrid storage concept is being developed in HyStEPS to increase the storage capacity of existing steam accumulators by up to 40%. The laboratory hybrid accumulators will be designed, built, the control and regulation developed and finally tested under operating conditions. Successful implementation promises a high potential for increasing efficiency while at the same time ensuring cost-effective implementation of the technology.

MAIN GOALS

Operational test of a laboratory prototype of an innovative hybrid storage system

40% increase in storage capacity

Enabling economic energy efficiency measures